

Limit state approach for structurally informed design of shells composed of interlocking blocks

Elham MOUSAVIAN*, Claudia CASAPULLA

* Department of Structures for Engineering and Architecture, University of Napoli Federico II
Via Forno vecchio, 36, 80134 - Napoli, Italy
elham.mousavian@unina.it

Abstract

This work demonstrates an extension of limit analysis with concave model to design 3D assemblages of dry jointed interlocking rigid blocks with orthotropic sliding resistance. A digital framework is developed to design and analyse the structural feasibility of assemblages of interlocking blocks. The sliding resistance is defined as a function of the geometric properties of the interlocking interface. Adjusting the geometric parameters, designers can modify the infeasible models to be stable. The limit states are governed by two types of failure planes including dry joints and fracture strips between the locks and the main body of the block. These planes are merged and simplified to an orthotropic interface between two blocks. Then, the interface is abstracted to a number of point contact points distributed on lock centrelines, at which the stress resultants are computed by solving the equilibrium problem under proper sliding constraints. Applying this method, the limit conditions for several single layer shells with hexahedral units assembled with stack bond are illustrated.

Keywords: concave limit analysis, interlocking blocks, non-isotropic sliding resistance, structurally informed computer aided design.

1. Introduction

Limit analysis using point contact formulation (introduced by Livesley [1]) has been widely used to model the discrete nature of assemblages of rigid blocks, mainly for masonry structures. This model is less computationally expensive comparing to finite element [2] and discrete element methods [3], yet highly accurate to analyse the structural feasibility of rigid block assemblages. According to this formulation, the structural model consists of rigid bodies with failure planes (contact interfaces) as their boundaries, where internal forces are distributed on. The limit state formulation has been developed for the contact interfaces with infinite [4] and finite isotropic frictions [5, 6]. Still, modelling of contact interfaces with non-isotropic sliding resistance is an open problem.

Interlocking blocks with a number of locks on their faces keeping the blocks together can be considered as units with non-isotropic sliding resistance. As shown in [7-9] through experimental tests, the interlocking interfaces increase the block sliding resistance without adhesives during or after the construction [10]. This paper extends the Livesley's contact model to corrugated interlocking interfaces having rectangular cross section. The approach is extendable to other cross sections though. For such interface, the sliding resistance is different along and normal to the locks (orthotropic). The assemblage is subjected to any types of external forces and torques.

The extended contact formulation of the paper introduces the orthotropic sliding resistance as a function of the geometric parameters of interlocking interfaces and therefore considers this modelling as a structurally informed design problem. Interlocking blocks with customized shape can be manufactured

by advanced machines such as CNC mills. The key motivation of the paper is to provide a computationally efficient method to design structurally feasible assemblages, via tuning the geometric parameters of interlocking interfaces, beside exploring various geometries for the structure and its blocks with interfaces previously constrained to be normal to the flow of forces [11] or to satisfy isotropic frictional constraint [12].

The authors of this paper earlier introduced a convex or surface contact model for interlocking corrugated interfaces [13] of semi-circular arches. The convex model idealized the assemblage through finding the stress state at a single point on an interface. This paper extends Livesley's concave or point contact model, using several points to abstract the contact interfaces. This approach suits the non-isotropic nature of the interlocking interfaces better than the convex model. In the following first this concave contact model is introduced. Then, the design workflow and the results of the framework are demonstrated in Sections 3 and 4, respectively.

2. Concave contact model for interlocking blocks

As introduced above, the discrete structural model consists of rigid bodies with failure planes as their boundaries, where internal forces are distributed on. For an interlocking interface (Figure 1a), the failure planes are assumed to be the **dry joints** between two interlocking blocks (blue strips) together with the **fracture planes** at which each block might crack (red strips in Figure 1b). The main body of the block is assumed rigid enough so that other types of potential fracture planes are avoided.

The dry joints can only rock/separate when normal forces on them are in tension or slide along the direction parallel to the locks when violating the Coulomb's friction constraint. The fracture planes slide or twist when the shear or torsion yielding conditions are reached, respectively. To simplify the model of the stress state, these two types of strips are merged (Figure 1c). Extending the concave contact model introduced by [1] to an interlocking interface, the merged failure planes are abstracted to a number of points. For a structurally feasible model, the internal forces on these points satisfy the equilibrium conditions and a set of constraints preventing the failures described above. For such an interlocking interface, at each point, the normal component of the internal force r^n is in compression; the tangential component of internal forces along the locks r^t satisfies the Coulomb's friction law and the tangential component of internal forces normal to the locks r^l is less than the shear resistance at the point (Figure 1c).

Figure 1: a) Two interlocking blocks kept together by the locks; b) dry joints (blue strips) and fracture planes (red strips), at which failure may occur; c) merged strip and point contacts distributed on their centrelines

To find the shear resistance at a point contact, first the lock is abstracted to its linear centreline, on which the tangential forces are distributed, uniformly or non-uniformly (Figures 2a,c). The lock is resistant when at each point along its length the force per unit length f_b is less than the shear resistance per unit length (yield force) $f_y = (\tau_k s)$ [13], where s is the lock thickness and τ_k is the material shear strength. In future work this resistance will be calibrated through experimental tests, similarly to what carried out in [14] for wooden interlocked pieces.

When the forces are distributed uniformly, the total shear resistance T_0 at the whole fracture plane between a lock and the main body of the block equals $(\tau_k s b)$, where b is the lock length (Figures 2c,d). For a non-uniform distribution of the forces, the total shear resistance at the fracture plane T_r is lower than T_0 (Figures 2c,d), so that $f_b \leq f_y$. Based on that, the distribution of the tangential forces can be abstracted by a number of point loads along the lock centreline, under the constraint that their resultant is $\leq T_0$. Thus, the shear resistance at each point i on a lock centreline can be a portion of T_0 through a weight p_i , so that $\sum_{i=1}^n p_i = 1$.

A validation test is now introduced for two options of point distribution, involving the number of points and weighting rules. Option 1 presents two points at $1/6$ distance to the end points of the centrelines (Figures 2e); the shear resistance at each point is $T_0/2$. Option 2 displays three points at the end points and the mid-point of the centrelines; the shear resistance at these points are shown in Figure 2f.

Figure 2: a) Generic lock; b) centrelines (C.L.) of the fracture planes between the locks and the main bodies of the blocks; c) uniform and non-uniform distributions of the tangential force on the lock centreline; d) limiting resultants of the two distributions; e) Option 1 and f) Option 2 for point distribution

The validation test is carried out to compare the sliding resistance obtained by these two options with the sliding resistance obtained by the literature convex formulation and experimental test [15] performed on two dry stacked tuff blocks subjected to different combinations of loading. For this comparison, only the interactions between torsion and tangential force are taken into consideration. These were executed by applying a lateral horizontal force with different eccentricities on the upper block, while the lower block was completely fixed.

The block dimensions and applied forces are reported in Figure 3a, while Figure 3b represents the configuration of point loads according to the point contact model Option 1, where T_0 at each lock is half of the total interface sliding resistance when pure tangential force is applied. Figure 3c shows different yield curves for the torsion-tangential force interaction related to: experimental results [15] (black dots); the convex method presented in [15] (dash red curve); the proposed Option 1 (blue dash-dot curve) and Option 2 (green continuous curve) for point distribution. While Option 1 provides conservative results, Option 2 shows a better agreement with the real behaviour of the interface.

Once defined the model of point distribution, the equilibrium problem under the limiting conditions is formulated as follows:

$$\begin{cases} C_{eq} \cdot \vec{r} + \vec{E} = 0 \\ r_{i,j}^n \leq 0 \\ |r_{i,j}^{t1}| \leq \mu |r_{i,j}^n| \\ |r_{i,j}^{t2}| \leq p_{i,j} T_0 \end{cases} \quad \forall i \in \text{merged strip } j; \sum_{i=1} p_{i,j} = 1 \quad (1)$$

where C_{eq} is the coefficient matrix, \vec{r} is a vector of all normal and tangential components of internal forces and \vec{E} is a vector of all external forces EF and torques ET . In this framework, the external force vector always includes the block weight which is obtained through the block volume multiplied by density.

Figure 3: a) Block dimensions and one of the loading combinations on two dry stacked blocks experimentally investigated [15]; b) outline of internal forces using the point contact model-Option 1; c) compared results for torsion-shear interactions

3. Design process

This section introduces the design process including the proposed modelling and structural analysis procedure. The new computational framework for limit analysis of interlocking block assemblages presented in this paper is a plug-in for grasshopper editor which is developed using c# language. The plug-in consists of five grasshopper (GH) components for 1) modelling the rigid blocks and an assemblage of such blocks, 2) modelling the interlocking interfaces, 3) determining the boundary conditions, 4) determining the external forces and torques and 5) implementing the analysis of the designed model (grey boxes in Figure 4). Figure 4 displays the design workflow and each function of the GH components in detail. All the inputs marked by the pink lines can be modified parametrically during the shape exploration. Outputs are marked by the blue lines.

This workflow is designed to model and analyse a single layer assemblage of blocks with grid pattern, where the main body of the blocks are hexahedron units. The main body of each block must have flat faces. As shown in Figure 5, the gridlines are divided into two series u and v . The overall shell can be closed along a v gridline to build a ring and can be converged towards the shell apex and be closed along a u gridline to form a radial grid (Figure 5b).

Figure 4: Design workflow

When the model is closed along a v gridline, the overlapped faces can be regarded as interfaces shared between two blocks. To use the coefficient matrix C_{eq} of Eq. (1) for such a model, a new set of constraints are added keeping the values of the internal forces on those overlapped faces equal in the opposite directions. When the closed surface is converged towards the upper side of the surface and is closed at

the last u gridline, a key unit is considered, and C_{eq} of Eq. (1) is updated by concatenating a row to it to equilibrate internal forces on the key unit.

In this workflow, the coordinate of the corners can be modified parametrically. Verifying the correctness of the assemblage topology and the flatness of the block faces during the initial modelling or the modification is beyond the framework of this paper and will be addressed in further works.

The linear system of Eq. (1) is solved by least square optimization using MATLAB's lsqin method with linear equality and non-equality constraints. The implementation of the computational setup is validated through comparing the minimum thickness of a hemispherical dome with conventional blocks subjected to its own weight obtained by this framework with those obtained by [4, 16] (Figure 5c). The results specifically validate that the set-up is capable of analysing the closed surface converged towards the apex through the explained amendments on C_{eq} for the open surfaces.

Figure 5: a) Normal grid (stacked) bonding pattern and b) radial grid bonding pattern; c) comparison of the thinnest hemispherical dome obtained by the proposed method and by [4, 16]

4. Results

Two examples are provided to study the interaction of: 1) orientation of locks and friction coefficient and 2) type of interfaces (conventional and interlocking) and friction coefficient.

Example 1. The first example is composed of three blocks (Figures 6a) with vertical interfaces between the blocks (yellow faces in Figures 6c,d). The assemblage is under the weight of the blocks whose density is 1 N/m^3 . Two faces, represented in blue in Figure 6b, are the supports transferring the forces to the ground. The orientation of the locks on the vertical interfaces varies during the shape exploration (Table 1). Figures 6c,d show two models with the vertical and horizontal locks, respectively. The concave model Option 1 displayed in Figure 2 is selected for the analysis. The shear strength is 10 N/m^2 . The number of locks at each interface is three.

Figure 6: a) Input model; b) boundary conditions; c and d) models with vertical and horizontal locks

For the case with vertical locks, the tangential forces at the interlocking interfaces are along the locks, therefore the sliding resistance is only governed by the Coulomb's friction law. The case can resist against sliding when the friction coefficient is more than 0.3. For the case with horizontal locks, the tangential forces at the interlocking interfaces are normal to the locks. As a result, the sliding resistance is only governed by the shear resistance of the locks and the model is stable even with the friction

coefficient equal to 0. The minimum friction coefficient needed for stability of the models with different lock orientations is represented in Table 1.

Table 1: Minimum friction coefficient for different lock orientations

Orientation (degree)	0	10	20	30	40	50	60	70	80	90
minimum friction coefficient	0	0.05	0.11	0.15	0.19	0.23	0.26	0.28	0.29	0.3

Example 2. The second example is composed of sixteen blocks (Figure 7a), under their own weight, where density is determined 1 N/m^3 and supporting faces are represented in blue in Figure 7b. Two cases are studied: 1) all interfaces are conventional flat faces (Figure 7c); 2) the interfaces along u and v gridlines are interlocking faces (Figure 7d). Interfaces in one direction are modelled with three locks (at each interface) with the orientation of 0.8 radians with respect to the block edge, while the interfaces in the other direction have three locks as well, but orientation of 2 radians. Both concave model options were used for the analysis. The shear strength is 10 N/m^2 .

Implementing concave model Options 1, the friction coefficient for the case with conventional blocks must be more than 0.23. Using concave model Option 2, this minimum value is reduced to 0.21. The computation time for Options 1 and 2 are 6.6 and 8.6 seconds, respectively, considering the larger number of points for Option 2. Whatever Option is implemented, the minimum friction coefficient for the case with the interlocking blocks is 0. This shows that when the shear strength is large enough, the model with interlocking interfaces can be stable with zero frictional resistance, while the minimum friction coefficient for such model with conventional flat interfaces is 0.23 or 0.21, depending on the model of point contact distribution.

Figure 7: a) Input model; b) boundary conditions; cases with c) conventional blocks in two directions; and e) interlocking blocks in two directions analysed by concave model Option 1

4. Conclusion

The paper presents a digital framework for structurally-informed design of shells composed of interlocking blocks. The applied structural analysis method is an extension of the concave contact model to interlocking interfaces and the model is developed for corrugated interfaces with rectangular cross section. These can be idealized as interfaces with orthotropic sliding resistance, with components normal to and along the locks governed by lock shear strength and Coulomb's friction law, respectively. In the future the contact model can be extended to other geometries for the cross section.

The sliding resistance is defined as a function of geometric properties of the locks including their number and orientation. Therefore, the framework considers those properties as parameters which can be adjusted by the users to check the stability of the model. Material properties including the friction coefficient and shear strength are other variables which can be changed parametrically. In further works,

automated procedures will be developed which tunes the geometric properties to make an infeasible model feasible. Accordingly, the infeasibility caused by the violation of sliding constraints will be measured and minimized through adjusting the geometric parameters of interlocking interfaces.

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